

Cross-site investigation on head-related and headphone transfer functions: variabilities in relation to loudness balancing

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Abstract

Headphone transfer function (HpTF) and head-related transfer function (HRTF) measurements are crucial in acoustic science and in binaural virtual acoustic applications. Yet, their measurement set-up, procedure or post-processing is different for nearly every lab, especially for the HRTF measurements. To compare findings between different labs, these measurement deviations have to be quantified alongside with their influence on perceptual aspects. In the scope of a cross-site investigation on loudness balancing between headphone and loudspeaker listening, a set of HpTFs with three different headphones (open, closed, insert earphones) and HRTF close to the eardrum were measured in 14 participants travelling to two different measurement sites at Aachen and Oldenburg.

Though set-ups for measuring the HRTF are very different between sites, the gathered HRTFs are quite consistent across them. For the measured HpTFs, across sites the open headphones consistently yield a slightly lower variability in the range from 70 to 5000 Hz than the closed one while the insert earphones exhibit much higher variabilities and a limited range of reproducible results. The difference in loudness balancing across labs could well be predicted by site-specific systematic differences in HpTFs with the exception of 1 kHz narrowband stimulus. This clearly indicates the limits in comparability of HpTFs and loudness balancing across labs and the importance of using headphones with high repeatability like the open ones used in this investigation.

1 Introduction

With the advent of three-dimensional video capturing and consumer products for playback such as head-mounted displays, correct spatial audio presentation is desired for immersive experiences. Binaural playback over headphones is the most economic, easiest to

set-up and most flexible solution and therefore typically used these days. To increase the authenticity of these methods, individual head-related transfer functions (HRTFs) are usually considered ideal for binaural synthesis with playback over headphones compensated by individual headphone transfer functions (HpTF) [1]. Rather complex multi-loudspeaker set-ups and methods for performing HRTF measurements have been implemented at multiple research labs (see [2] for an overview), however, no ubiquitous method to do so has been established and it cannot be expected that unified standards for this task will be established. On the contrary, HpTFs are directly measured on ear simulators or humans, but they underlie a certain dependency on fitting of the headphone to the head which changes with every taking-off and putting-on (repositioning) of the headphones [3, 4, 5, 6]. In addition, both HRTFs and HpTFs depend on the recording location in the ear, thus increasing the likelihood that the resulting functions critically depend on the exact procedure pursued in each laboratory and with each individual subject. The aim of the current study therefore is to estimate the expected variation across laboratories in relation to the variability across subjects, and to evaluate these variations by their respective consequences regarding the estimated level at eardrum in a loudness balancing experiment.

Hence, in a cross-site comparison between the lab sites in Aachen and Oldenburg, a dataset of HRTFs and HpTFs for three different headphones were measured with probe microphones close to the eardrum in 14 participants travelling to both measurement sites. Even though these probe tube measurements are more time consuming than blocked-entrance measurements, we employed this method since any kind of ear canal entrance measurement would not be applicable for insert earphones that were included in the study, as well as to correctly capture effects of acoustic loading of the ear by headphones [5, 7]. Additionally, the probe tube placement close to the eardrum is an anatomically well-defined location, as opposed to insertion at

81 the blocked ear canal entrance.

82 Literature on reproducibility measurements of indi- 139
 83 vidual HRTFs is limited. The potential influence of 140
 84 the lab has been highlighted, e.g., by comparison of 141
 85 HRTFs measured on the same dummy head in dif- 142
 86 ferent labs by Andreopoulou et al. [8]. Yet, com- 143
 87 parable studies on humans are rare. Møller et al. 144
 88 [9] investigated inter-participant variations and re- 145
 89 peatability measurements on one subject. Riederer 146
 90 [10] investigated mainly intra-subject effects in the 147
 91 same hardware and lab set-up. He also investigated 148
 92 the influence on HRTF variability by changing the 149
 93 experimenter which is comparable to the presented 150
 94 study. Andreopoulou et al. [11] investigated the in- 151
 95 fluence by changing a number of variables, namely: 152
 96 the room used, loudspeaker set-up, repositioning the 153
 97 microphones and the participants alignment in the 154
 98 loudspeaker array. Besides the fact that they investi- 155
 99 gate blocked ear canal measurements, the study is the 156
 100 closest to the presented study as can be seen in 2.1.2. 157
 101 All investigations point towards higher intra-subject 158
 102 repeatability for frequencies up to the ear canal reso- 159
 103 nance (between 2000 Hz and 3000 Hz) and above up 160
 104 to 5000 Hz. 161

105 For literature on HpTF variability, a variety of inves- 162
 106 tigations can be found. To name a few: Shaw [12] 163
 107 investigated ear canal pressures due to different head- 164
 108 phone types and three repositions. Møller et al. [5] 165
 109 measured 14 different headphones on 40 participants 166
 110 at the blocked ear canal. Kulkarni and Colburn [3] in- 167
 111 vestigated the variability due to repositioning of head- 168
 112 phones on an artificial head. More recently, inter- and 169
 113 intra-subject variability of blocked ear canal measure- 170
 114 ments have been investigated by Völk [6]. All studies 171
 115 conclude low and smooth variabilities due to reposi- 172
 116 tioning for lower frequencies (around 1 to 2 dB), mod- 173
 117 erate deviations around the ear canal resonance (2 to 174
 118 3 dB) but still low up to 5000 to 6000 Hz, and higher 175
 119 variations (up to 10 to 15 dB) for frequencies above 176
 120 10 kHz. The most likely reason for the observed vari- 177
 121 abilities are high-Q notches changing in occurring fre- 178
 122 quency and magnitude. To the authors' knowledge, 179
 123 variations in HpTF in one subject measured across 180
 124 different laboratories have not been reported before, 181
 125 except for the results of the presented study already 182
 126 shown in a companion paper [13] for the open head- 183
 127 phones. 184

128 Besides being used for assessing the variability in 185
 129 physical parameters across laboratories, the obtained 186
 130 transfer functions are utilized in an evaluation of the 187
 131 loudness mismatch between loudspeaker and head- 188
 132 phone presentation in a companion paper [13]. Such 189
 133 mismatches, i.e. level differences at eardrum at equal 190
 134 loudness, have been reported repeatedly since the 191
 135 1940s [14, 15, 16] mostly for low frequencies and 192
 136 closed headphones. The phenomenon was named by 193
 137 the amount of mismatch occurring at low frequen- 194
 138 cies: "The missing 6dB". In 2011 Völk et al. [17]

139 showed that the loudness mismatch disappears when 140
 141 applying binaural synthesis and compensation of the 142
 143 headphone transfer function in a blind comparison 144
 145 paradigm. They assume that the loudness mismatch 146
 147 is caused by a mismatch in time and phase relations 148
 149 between left and right ear. Nevertheless, the results 150
 151 from our earlier study [13] with a larger variation 152
 153 across listening conditions showed that some unex- 154
 155 plained mismatch still remains - especially across the 156
 157 anechoic rooms in Aachen and Oldenburg, thus call- 158
 159 ing for a closer look at the underlying variabilities in 160
 161 transfer functions for both sites. 162

163 The current paper therefore quantifies the cross-site 164
 165 effects on HRTF and HpTF measurements as well 166
 167 as loudness mismatch experiments. 14 participants 168
 169 travelled to both laboratories, one in Aachen and 170
 171 one in Oldenburg. In each lab a full HRTF set as 172
 173 well as the HpTF for three different headphones were 173
 174 measured. As detailed in [13], a loudness balancing 174
 175 listening test was conducted where the subjects ad- 176
 177 justed headphone playback to equal loudness of loud- 177
 178 speaker playback of the same stimulus. Using individ- 178
 179 ual HRTFs and HpTFs, the appropriate levels created 179
 180 at the eardrum, and the mismatch, i.e. level difference 180
 181 at equal loudness, was calculated. While the previous 181
 182 paper explored several factors influencing this mis- 182
 183 match (room, stimulus, binaural parameters of head- 183
 184 phone playback), the present study focusses on how 184
 185 the mismatch, and in particular apparent disparities 185
 186 between sites, could be explained by cross-site differ- 186
 187 ences between the underlying HRTF and HpTF data. 187
 188 To this end, we restrict ourselves to the loudness bal- 188
 189 ancing results obtained in anechoic environments with 189
 190 diotic headphone playback, but consider the results of 190
 191 all three headphones and a wider frequency range of 191
 192 the employed stimuli (125 Hz to 12 kHz). 192

2 Methods 175

2.1 Technical measurements 176

2.1.1 Probe tube measurements 177

178 To measure the sound pressure level close to the 178
 179 eardrum, a probe tube was inserted into the ear 179
 180 canal until participants noticed a soft contact with the 180
 181 eardrum. After slightly pulling back the probe tube, 181
 182 the microphone and its housing were fixed with medi- 182
 183 cal tape on the subjects' cheek the ear to minimize the 183
 184 influence of the measurement device on the fitting of 184
 185 the headphones and on the incidence sound field. The 185
 186 76 mm long probe tubes (Type 76109MBB, Precision 186
 187 Cast Plastic Parts, Redding, CA, USA) were used on 187
 188 ER7C series probe microphones (ER7C, Etymotic Re- 188
 189 search, Elk Grove Village, IL, USA). Once placed and 189
 190 fixed, the probe tubes were not repositioned between 190
 191 HpTF and HRTF measurement. 191

2.1.2 HRTFs

Both sides have very different approaches to measure the head-related transfer functions as described in the following.

In Oldenburg, the measurements were done in an anechoic chamber (volume: 274m³; wedge length: 0.6m) with a fixed loudspeaker set-up. A fixed 3D loudspeaker array comprising circles at different elevations is employed. The loudspeakers are positioned with intervals of 7.5 degree in the horizontal plane and 30 degree in azimuth for elevations of -30 and 30 degree. At 60 degree elevation a spacing of 60 degree is chosen, leading to sum of 87 directions. A more detailed description of the set-up and the procedure can be found in [18]. The participants were seated and equipped with absorbers on their legs to suppress reflections. The ear height of the participant was adapted to align with the acoustic axis of the loudspeakers mounted in the horizontal plane. Loudspeakers used were two-way Genelec 8030 with two types of drivers, one 130 mm in diameter and one 19 mm. The measurement time in Oldenburg was about 30 seconds, and participants' head position and orientation were tracked to provide visual feedback about their alignment with the loudspeaker set-up [19]. The measured impulse responses were time windowed using a frequency dependent time window approach [20] and divided by the microphone sensitivity and loudspeaker responses separately. Below 60 Hz, the impulse responses were extrapolated to a flat response. The final response was time shifted by 1 ms and truncated to 356 samples including a 12 sample ramp at the beginning and a 24 sample ramp at the end. A sample rate of 44100 Hz was used.

In Aachen, participants were measured standing on a turntable in a hemi-anechoic chamber (volume: 296m³; wedge length: 0.8m) with a vertical 64 loudspeaker arc as described in [21]. The loudspeaker closest to the horizontal plane differs in elevation by -0.54 degree. A neck-rest was used to suppress movement while the participant was rotated and the set-up adapted to match the participants ear height with the centre point of the arc. Loudspeakers used were one inch (25.4 mm) Tang Band W1-2025SA. To reduce measurement time and to match directions used in the Oldenburg set-up the horizontal resolution was set to 7.5 degrees resulting in 3072 measured directions and a duration of about nine minutes for one participant. No feedback about the participants position was given. The impulse responses were time windowed, to exclude floor reflections, and divided by the complex transfer function of the microphones measured in the empty arc. Below 500 Hz the data is extrapolated to 0 dB at 0 Hz preserving the phase information. The final response was time shifted and truncated to 356 samples at a sample rate of 44100 Hz.

The differences in measurement procedures summa-

rized are (Aachen - Oldenburg):

- participants posture (standing - seated)
- participants movement (turntable - fixed)
- feedback to the participants about their alignment with the set-up (none - tracked)
- number of direction measured (3072 - 87)
- type of loudspeaker used (passive one-way 25.4 mm driver - active two-way 130 and 19 mm driver)
- post-processing
 - one reference measurement including microphone and loudspeaker - independent compensation of loudspeaker and microphones
 - different low frequency cut-off (500 Hz - 60 Hz)
- duration of measurement (9 minutes vs. 30 seconds)

2.1.3 HpTFs

HpTFs were measured in Oldenburg and Aachen with duplicates of the same sound card with integrated high-power headphone amplifier (ADI-2 PRO FS, RME, Haimhausen, Germany). The headphones used were repositioned by the experimenter between measurements and each headphone was measured eight times for each participant to account for variabilities due to fitting [22]. Measurements that revealed obvious faults, e.g. broadband level reduction due to clogging or squeezing of probe tubes, or those including false notches due to microphone misplacements, were excluded. The probe tubes were not repositioned between measurements.

The sensitivity and frequency response of the probe tube microphones were acquired via the substitution method as described in IEC 61094-8 [23] in the anechoic chambers. In Aachen they were compared to a GRAS 40AF half inch microphone while in Oldenburg an eighth inch GRAS 46-DP1 was used. The measurements were shifted to a common delay and windowed to a length of 93 ms (4096 samples at 44100 Hz). Hence, the HpTFs are described as a transfer factor from a given headphone voltage input to a measured sound pressure close to the eardrum, i.e. [Pa/V], containing the characteristics of the headphone, its fitting and the ear physiology of the individual participant. Headphones measured were the circumaural, open type Sennheiser HD650 (Sennheiser, Wedemark, Germany), the circumaural, closed housing Beyerdynamic DT770 Pro 250 Ohm (Beyerdynamic, Heilbronn, Germany) and insert earphones Etymotic ER4-PT with double silicon domes (Etymotic Research, Elk Grove Village, IL, USA). The latter one will also be considered as part of the generic term 'headphones'. The selection of the headphones is somewhat arbitrary, but

they are all in wide spread use. Differences between the labs are mainly expected due to post-processing and in acquiring of the microphone sensitivity and its frequency response. At Aachen and Oldenburg, different pairs of headphones were used, which were acquired in one batch.

2.2 Sound pressure level estimation during headphone and loudspeaker presentation

To calculate the eardrum sound pressure level during headphone presentation the stored stimulus S_{dig} in digital units [DU] is multiplied with the gain G [V/DU] which was set during the listening test to achieve equal loudness and which already includes the digital to analogue converter. It is then convolved with the previously, individually measured HpIR [Pa/V], which is the inverse Fourier transform of the HpTF (see section 2.1.3), to acquire a pressure signal at the eardrum. Both ear sides and signals obtained using all eight repeated HpIRs were averaged in terms of RMS (root-mean-square) values. Variability due to repositioning of the headphones, between subjects and between labs, is analysed in section 3.2. For the eardrum levels during loudspeaker presentation the calculation is different. Prior to each listening test session, the loudspeaker presentation was calibrated using a calibrated, half-inch free-field microphone (46AF, G.R.A.S., Holte, Denmark) pointing towards the loudspeaker to ensure a playback level at the receiver position of 65 phon. The calibration was done for each stimulus separately and provided a one channel free-field stimulus S_{rec} [Pa] as sound pressure signal. The recorded stimulus was then convolved with the corresponding two-channel HRIR, which is the inverse Fourier transform of the HRTF (see section 2.1.2), to obtain the sound pressure waveform at the eardrums.

To understand the influence of measured HpTF and HRTF values on the results of the listening test we briefly formulate the mismatch (with '*' denoting a convolution) as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Mismatch [dB]} = & 20 \cdot \log_{10} \left(\left(S_{\text{dig}} [\text{DU}] \cdot G \left[\frac{\text{V}}{\text{DU}} \right] \right) * \text{HpIR} \left[\frac{\text{Pa}}{\text{V}} \right] \right) \\ & - 20 \cdot \log_{10} \left(S_{\text{rec}} [\text{Pa}] * \text{HRIR} \left[\frac{\text{Pa}}{\text{Pa}} \right] \right) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Therefore, higher levels in an HpTF measurement will generally increase the observed mismatch, whereas higher values in the HRTF measurement will decrease it. Both transfer functions were measured in the (hemi-) anechoic chambers of the appropriate site.

2.3 Listening test

A loudness balancing test was conducted in Aachen and Oldenburg including the 14 participants traveling to both sites. Participants had to state whether they perceived the headphone or the loudspeaker presentation as louder, taking on and off the headphone between the presentations. A 1-up-1-down two alternate forced choice (AFC) design adapted the headphone level until equal loudness perception was achieved. Participants were seated and the loudspeaker positioned 2.25m in front of them. More details about the listening test can be found in [13].

As independent variables three different headphones used (see section 2.1.3), two rooms (see section 2.1.2) and nine stimuli were used. As stimuli one-third octave band noises (tbn) were used with centre frequencies at 125 Hz, 250 Hz, 500 Hz, 1000 Hz, 2000 Hz, 4000 Hz, 8000 Hz and 12 kHz. The overall length of each stimulus was 1 second including 20 ms ramps to fade in and out. To cover combined effects a wide band noise between 20 Hz and 4 kHz was used with the same energy in the 17 critical frequency bands as described by Zwicker [24] and will be further related to as 'uen17' as short term for unified excitation noise.

3 Results

3.1 HRTFs

The upper row of figure 1 shows all magnitude spectra taken in Aachen and Oldenburg for a frontal source, i.e. each participant is represented with two measurements here. The measurements converge towards lower frequencies as they are extrapolated towards 0 Hz. Frequencies above approximately 6000 Hz show higher fluctuations. The individual differences are caused by individually distributed centre frequencies of dips and notches that are shifted against other subjects due to individual geometries. This plot displays both inter-individual and cross-site deviations.

For each participant, two HRTF measurements were conducted: one in Aachen and one in Oldenburg. The difference of these measurements (across laboratories) is plotted as grey line for each participant in the bottom row of figure 1. As only one HRTF dataset per subject and laboratory site was gathered, the influence of intra-subject repeatability at one site can not be quantified with the data present.

Up to 6000 Hz the median difference across laboratory sites is below 2.7 dB with an exception around 1600 Hz (left ear, median: 3.2 dB, range: 0.11 dB to 5.02 dB). Another systematic deviation can be seen at a frequency of about 500 Hz (which corresponds to the extrapolation start for Aachen HRTFs, see section 2.1.2) exhibiting a small effect (left ear, median: +0.94 dB, range: +0.12 to +1.49 dB). For higher frequencies, a tendency towards negative deviations

Figure 1: The upper row shows HRTF magnitude levels over a continuous frequency spectrum of a frontal sound source of participants that were measured at both sites using probe tube microphones positioned close to the eardrum. Left diagram relates to the left and the right diagram to the right ear. Red line shows the median, in transparent blue the range of 75% of measurement data around the median is plotted. Gray lines indicate an individual measurement. Dashed lines indicate a measurement in Aachen, dotted lines measurements in Oldenburg. The bottom row shows the difference in measurements for each participant between the HRTF measured in Aachen and Oldenburg for a frontal source. For the bottom diagrams, the median is averaged with 1/12th octave band moving averaging window.

398 (higher values in Oldenburg compared to the ones in
 399 Aachen) can be observed. The prominent notches differ
 400 between left ear (about -8 dB median at 9400 Hz)
 401 and right ear (-9.5 dB median at around 11.5 kHz and
 402 -12 dB median at 13.8 kHz).

403 3.2 HpTFs

404 3.2.1 Variability across transfer functions

405 Figure 2 shows the HpTF magnitude spectra for the
 406 three different headphones used. Note that the range
 407 on the y-axis is wider for the ER4 measurements.
 408 Comparable to figure 1, this plots combines inter-
 409 subject effects as well as across-site ones. Each grey
 410 line displays the mean of the magnitude over up to
 411 eight repetitions. The amount of deviation in low fre-
 412 quencies dependent on the headphone type used and
 413 is small for the HD650, moderate for the DT770 and
 414 highest for the ER4 insert earphones. Up to 5000
 415 Hz differences between measurements are small com-
 416 pared to those for higher frequencies. All HpTFs have
 417 a maximum around 3000 Hz (ear canal resonance) and
 418 decrease towards very high frequencies. The HD650
 419 shows the flattest overall frequency curve. The DT770
 420 has a wide, prominent notch between 200 and 250 Hz
 421 and a smaller one around 3800 Hz that can be ob-

served on both ear sides. For the ER4 the decreasing
 422 curve towards very low frequencies as well as the in-
 423 creasing variance towards those frequencies is notice-
 424 able as well as a peak around 15500 Hz.
 425

426 3.2.2 Intra-subject comparison

427 After measuring the HpTF of a participant, it usually
 428 can not be assured that the fitting of the headphones
 429 is invariant against repositioning during the listen-
 430 ing test. Especially in loudness balancing tests head-
 431 phones usually have to be repositioning many times.
 432 Figure 3 shows the difference between the maximum
 433 magnitude level measured in eight repetitions of fit-
 434 ting and the minimum level for each frequency bin.
 435 For the open HD650 these differences are small (less
 436 than 1.4 dB for the upper boundary) between 90 to
 437 2500 Hz. Between 2500 and 5000 Hz the deviations
 438 slowly increase up to 2.8 dB for the upper bound and
 439 a median of 1.4 dB. For higher frequencies the vari-
 440 ation increases more rapid and repeatability can not
 441 be assumed in a reasonable range.

442 For the DT770 a range between about 500 Hz and
 443 2300 Hz is below 1.5 dB for the upper bound with a
 444 median below 0.8 dB. Towards 90 Hz the variability
 445 slowly increases up to a value of 4.5 dB for the upper
 446 bound and 2.8 dB median on the right ear side. From

Figure 2: HpTF magnitude levels for participants measured in Aachen and Oldenburg separated by left and right ear. Plotted is the mean over eight repetitions of the frequency magnitude. The sound pressure was measured close to the eardrum using probe tubes. The range of the y-axis differs for the ER4 measurements at the bottom. Red line shows the median, in transparent blue the range of 75% of measurement data around the median is plotted. Gray lines indicate the mean of one individual participant over up to eight repetitions. Dashed lines indicate a measurement in Aachen, dotted lines measurements in Oldenburg.

447 2300 to 6000 Hz the variability also slowly increases
 448 up to a value of 3.8 dB for the upper bound and 2.5 dB
 449 for the median. For higher frequencies observations
 450 comparable to those of the HD650 can be made.

451 The ER4 has deviations up to 15 dB for the upper
 452 bound at 90 Hz with a median of 7.4 dB. Deviations
 453 decrease with increasing frequency due to the reduced
 454 influence of the random leakage effect of the insert
 455 earphone. In a range between 900 Hz and 3500 Hz the
 456 upper bound stays below 2.6 dB with a median below
 457 1.3 dB. From 3500 Hz towards 6000 Hz the deviations
 458 again increase slowly up to an upper bound of 6.4 dB
 459 and a median of 2.6 dB. Towards higher frequencies
 460 the deviations increase even faster than for the HD650
 461 and the DT770 .

3.2.3 Cross-site comparison

462
 463 Figure 4 shows the difference in magnitude between
 464 the mean of HpTF obtained in Aachen and Oldenburg
 465 ($HPTF_{Aachen} - HPTF_{Oldenburg}$) for the same partici-
 466 pant as grey line for all 14 subjects. It has to be noted
 467 that the cross-site effects plotted here are inherently
 468 influenced by the intra-subject variability as shown in
 469 the previous section. The measurements for HD650
 470 and the DT770 coincidence quite well in the range of
 471 the intra-subject variability up to 5000 Hz (see figure
 472 4). The only exception occurs on the left ear around
 473 2000 Hz which is mainly influenced by two measure-
 474 ments only. The ER4 insert earphones deviate more
 475 for the lower frequencies than can be predicted from
 476 intra-subject variability (see figure 4). No measure-
 477 ment deviations lie in the range of approximately 0
 478 to -10 dB which suggests a more systematic effect.
 479 For frequencies higher than 5000 Hz the variance of

Figure 3: Maximum deviations for repositioning the headphones eight times for each participant in Aachen and in Oldenburg. For each frequency the maximum level [dB] minus the minimum over up to eight repetitions is taken. Left diagram relates to the left and the right diagram to the right ear. Red line shows the median (smoothed by one-twelfth moving average window). In transparent blue the range of 75% of measurement data around the median is plotted. Gray lines indicate an individual measurement. Dashed lines indicate a measurement in Aachen, dotted lines measurements in Oldenburg.

480 deviation increases while the median does not show a
 481 consistent behaviour between ear sides or headphones.
 482 Towards higher frequencies the measurements done in
 483 Aachen result in a somewhat higher level especially in
 484 the region between 12 kHz and 13 kHz.

485 3.3 Listening test

486 Figure 5 shows the difference in eardrum sound pres-
 487 sure level between headphone and loudspeaker pre-
 488 sentation at equal loudness perception on the y-axis
 489 (see section 2.2), and the stimulus on the x-axis. The
 490 figure is separated into the two rooms under test.

491 Two-way ANOVAs were conducted for each room in-
 492 cluding a test of simple effects. Significant differences
 493 between headphones for a room-stimulus combination
 494 are marked in figure 5 with brackets above each con-
 495 dition. For the uen17 signal, the ER4 insert earphones
 496 differ significantly from the other two headphones in

both rooms. Additionally, the ER4 differs in the
 497 anechoic room in Oldenburg for the DT770 at tbn500
 498 (HD650: $p=0.056$) and for both headphones at the
 499 tbn250 stimulus. Significance of differences between
 500 stimuli are not marked in figure 5 to keep readability
 501 of the figure. In the Aachen anechoic chamber the re-
 502 spective mismatches for the tbn1000 and the tbn12000
 503 differ significantly from other stimuli. In the Olden-
 504 burg anechoic chamber the high frequency tbn8000
 505 and tbn12000 differ significantly from the lower ones,
 506 with further analysis revealing only a difference for
 507 the ER4 for this case and an additional difference to
 508 the uen17 stimulus.
 509

510 3.3.1 Cross-site comparison

Figure 6 shows the differences between the measure-
 511 ments and listening test results for the anechoic rooms
 512 in Aachen and Oldenburg. The symbols show the
 513

Figure 4: Deviations of the obtained HpTF spectra for each participant across sites for the HpTF magnitude spectra for the different headphones separated by left and right ear. Microphones were positioned close to the eardrum using probe tubes. Left diagram relates to the left and the right diagram to the right ear. Red line shows the median (smoothed by one-twelfth moving average window), in transparent blue the range of 75% of measurement data around the median is plotted. Gray lines indicate an individual measurement.

514 deviation in mismatches (Aachen minus Oldenburg)
 515 measured in the listening test plotted over frequency,
 516 with the red HD650 and the green ER4 symbols
 517 shifted in frequency for readability. Vertical dashed
 518 lines indicate the upper and lower boundaries of one-
 519 third bands employed for the listening tests. The solid
 520 lines show the mean deviation of HpTFs (see figure
 521 4) minus the mean deviation in HRTF (see figure 1
 522 bottom row) between Aachen and Oldenburg. If the
 523 lines in a one-third octave band and symbols would
 524 coincide, the physical difference in transfer-function
 525 measurements would fully explain the deviations in
 526 the listening test results between Aachen and Olden-
 527 burg. It should be noted that the symbols should not
 528 be compared to the value of the corresponding fre-
 529 quency but rather to the whole frequency band which
 530 is indicated by the vertical, dashed lines.

4 Discussion 531

4.1 HRTF measurements 532

533 The measurement conditions differed in various points
 534 between the labs as listed in section 2.1.2. Only the
 535 type of probe tube microphones used were the same
 536 and agreements on the final response (length, over-
 537 all window and data format) for better comparison as
 538 well as evaluation of the listening test were made. The
 539 measured HRTFs across laboratory sites and partic-
 540 ipants in figure 1 state an increasing variability with
 541 increasing frequency. Up to 6000 Hz the increase of
 542 variability and its absolute value is moderate (up to
 543 10 dB above 2000 Hz) while for higher frequencies
 544 variations up to 20 dB occur due to different notch
 545 centre frequencies.

546 The deviations across laboratory sites are reasonably
 547 small (median below 2.7 dB) up to 6000 Hz. Besides
 548 the very different approaches in measuring the HRTFs

Figure 5: Level mismatch obtained from the loudness balancing tests between headphone and loudspeaker presentation for three headphones and 14 subjects across two sites. Each smaller marker is the mean for one participant, each bigger marker the mean over all participants with the whisker indicating the standard deviation. The results are plotted as eardrum sound pressure level difference between headphone and loudspeaker presentation for the same perceived loudness. The x-axis denotes the presented stimulus and the figure is split into the two tested rooms. Each colour represents one specific headphone type.

549 and the set-up of the measurements, an inherent deviation due to intra-subject repeatability has to be
 550 taken into account. Riederer [10] utilizes one seated participant in the same laboratory and measurement
 551 set-up with microphones placed at the blocked ear canal to investigate intra-subject repeatability. The
 552 HRTFs were measured with three different experimenters inserting the microphones. For the frontal
 553 direction, differences for an expert experimenter can be found around 2.7 dB up to 3000 Hz and 10 dB
 554 and higher up to 10 kHz when using four repetitions. Measurements at the open ear canal (only two repetitions)
 555 showed similar deviations. The values increase with less thorough placed microphones (about 4.4 dB
 556 up to 3000 Hz). Møller et al. [9] analysed HRTF repeatability using probe microphones at the open
 557 ear canal entrance within the same lab but with only one participant repeated three times. For the frontal
 558 direction they show deviations around 1.5 dB up to about 5000 Hz and up to 15 dB variance above 7000
 559 Hz due to different notch behaviour. Another study by Andreopoulou et al. [11] investigated four partici-
 560 pants with 10 repeated measurements under comparable conditions to this study by changing the room and
 561 loudspeaker array as well as microphone repositioning and two different experimenters. Although they only
 562 show results for the whole dataset, the same principle applies in which frequencies up to 2000 Hz result in
 563 low variations (less than 5 dB) while for higher frequencies these deviations increase up to 15 dB.
 564
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579 Overall the deviations found do not exceed the expected variability due to repetition of the measurement
 580 reported on the literature. Yet, some details differ to the findings and can be mapped to laboratory
 581 influence. The observable systematic deviation at 500 Hz is most probably due to the interpolation
 582 start in the Aachen post-processing, yet is considerably small (less than 1.5 dB). The deviation around
 583 1600 Hz, which results from a notch in the Oldenburg data that is not present in the Aachen data, could be
 584 a change in posture for the different settings (seated vs. standing with neck-rest). Influence of a possible
 585 reflection from legs or knees are expected to affect lower frequencies [10, 18]. Also, influences of clothing
 586 as investigated by [10] and [25] do not point towards a narrow-band difference only that occurs in this
 587 region. Another explanation could be found in different angles of head pitch. As the effect is in a narrow band
 588 and can be observed for both ears equally, head rotation other than pitch angle seem unlikely. For the
 589 same reason, influence by a systematic participants' displacement from the reference point of the measurement
 590 set-up seems unlikely as it would affect the left and right side differently. Furthermore, the effect decreases
 591 with increasing distance of the incidence from the horizontal plane and vanishes about 45 degrees to the
 592 left or right side. In the median plane the effects shift towards lower frequencies for negative elevations
 593 to about 1100 to 1200 Hz at -20 degree and vanishes at an elevation of -30 degree. For positive elevation
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Figure 6: Differences in individual mismatch between anechoic rooms in Aachen and Oldenburg. Each small marker is the difference for one specific participant, bigger markers the mean over all participants. Whisker denote the standard deviation. Colours represent one specific headphone type. Solid lines show the calculated mean deviations in mismatch due to the HpTF and HRTF average deviation across sites. The x-axis indicates the frequency with vertical lines showing the boundaries of the one-third octave bands employed for the stimuli in the listening tests. The red markers for HD650 and the green markers for the ER4 are shifted in frequency for better readability.

609 angles the notch frequencies increases towards 2000
 610 to 2300 Hz at +20 degree and vanishes (or averages
 611 out) at +30 degree.

612 Another systematic difference can be observed around
 613 10 kHz in the shape of a notch followed by a peak.
 614 The frequency range and the wider characteristics of
 615 the deviation point toward a systematically different
 616 placement of the probe tubes. Even though the aim
 617 was to place them as close as possible to the eardrum,
 618 the placement was neither quantified nor measured
 619 and performed by different experimenter. Influence of
 620 different probe tube placements can be found in e.g.
 621 [26, 27] and match quite well with the observed devi-
 622 ations in terms of frequency, notch width and ampli-
 623 tude. Consequently, a peak following the notch would
 624 be expected when dividing two transfer functions with
 625 different notch centre frequencies.

626 It should be noted that the overall number of 14 par-
 627 ticipants under test in this study is compared to an
 628 overall number of 8 participants in all three referenc-
 629 ed studies together, with the downside of having only
 630 one repetition (and alteration of the higher number
 631 of influencing factors) in this study which can not be
 632 analysed separately.

633 4.2 HpTF measurements

634 The HpTF measurements show good repeatability up
 635 to about 5000 Hz between repositioning and across
 636 laboratory sites, and low variability across subjects.
 637 The DT770 shows slightly increased variability to-

wards lower frequencies whereas the HpTFs become
 unreliable for ER4 insert earphones for frequencies be-
 low 900 Hz with median variabilities up to 8 dB only
 due to repositioning around 70 Hz and variability of
 15 dB across subjects and laboratory sites at that fre-
 quency. Towards higher frequencies intra- and inter-
 subject variabilities increases for all headphones used
 whereas systematic influence across laboratory sites
 can only be observed at 10 kHz and above 13 kHz.

647 The results found for intra-subject variability due to
 648 headphone repositioning in figure 3 show that the fre-
 649 quency range for small deviations of up to ± 1 dB
 650 reaches up to 6000 Hz, which is comparable to the
 651 findings of Völk [6]. Even though their investigation
 652 focuses on open type headphones only and blocked
 653 ear canal measurements, it offers a good reference,
 654 especially for the HD650, because of its high num-
 655 ber of repetition and the utilization of both, inter-
 656 and intra-subject measurements. For the influence
 657 of repositioning the HD650 they found variabilities
 658 below 1 dB up to 6000 Hz with increased variabili-
 659 ties above these frequencies up to 6 dB whereas the
 660 present study shows higher deviations especially for
 661 frequencies above 13 kHz, which might relate to the
 662 use of probe tubes and the measured sensitivity for the
 663 compensation of the microphones. The same is true
 664 for the DT770, excluding the slight increase of vari-
 665 ability towards lower frequencies. Møller et al. [5] did
 666 similar investigations with one subject but multiple
 667 headphones. Again, the variation is low for frequen-
 668 cies up to 6000 Hz. Above these frequencies variabil-

669 ity increase mainly to slightly shifted peak and notch
 670 positions. The across subject effects are naturally af-
 671 fected by the intra-subject variabilities which seem
 672 to be a dominant factor for frequencies below 6000
 673 Hz where across subject deviations are comparable to
 674 the intra-subject ones as shown in both studies. For
 675 higher frequencies, the across subject deviations ex-
 676 ceed those for the intra-subjects ones as the centre
 677 frequencies of peaks and notches are highly individ-
 678 ual.

679 The differences across laboratories observed in the
 680 present study is small and well within the range of
 681 intra-subject deviations. Thus, for higher frequencies
 682 the probe tube measurements deviate a lot more. The
 683 dip around 10 kHz is similar to those found between
 684 HRTFs which relate to the microphone placement dif-
 685 ferences between the two sites as mentioned above.
 686 Additional a strong peak towards higher frequency
 687 can be seen caused by differences in the microphone
 688 compensation (see figure 7) that takes effect. Figure
 689 7 shows the transfer function of the post processed
 690 data of a Dirac pulse in Aachen and Oldenburg for
 691 the ER7C microphones, i.e. the microphone compen-
 692 sation. While deviations are considerably small below
 693 10 kHz, high deviations occur for higher frequencies
 694 that can be caused by different fixing of the probe
 695 tubes during sensitivity measurements. It should be
 696 noted that these compensations are also used for the
 697 HRTFs in Oldenburg, but not in Aachen (see section
 698 2.1.2).

699 Another aspect of fitting and leakage is the presence
 700 of the probe tube at the pinna cartilage. The probe
 701 tubes were only present during HpTF measurements
 702 but not during the loudness balancing task. A prob-
 703 able leakage effect of the probe tubes results in a
 704 lower measured amplitude for lower frequencies and,
 705 as shown in section 2.2, would lead to decreased mis-
 706 matches. Yet, this effect can not be observed in figure
 707 5. However, a tendency towards the inverse behaviour
 708 especially in the Oldenburg anechoic room supports
 709 the assumption that the effect of a carefully fitted
 710 ER4 during the HpTF measurements in comparison
 711 to an uncontrolled fitting during testing either dom-
 712 inates an effect of the presence of the probe tube or
 713 the probe tubes do not significantly affect the fitting.

714 4.3 Influence of measurement uncer- 715 tainties on the loudness mismatch

716 Between the settings in Aachen and Oldenburg the
 717 results of the loudness balancing experiment do agree
 718 quite well. In figure 6, it can be observed that the
 719 deviation in mismatch between sites is generally well
 720 within its standard deviation. Only at two frequencies
 721 deviations occur, namely at the 1000 Hz one-third oc-
 722 tave band and at 12 kHz. The latter can be mapped
 723 to the systematic differences in HpTFs (see also figure
 724 4) and the used microphone sensitivities. The differ-

Figure 7: Transfer function of the microphone compensation in the post processing in Aachen and Oldenburg smoothed by a one-sixth octave band moving average window. The bottom part shows the deviation Aachen minus Oldenburg. Note that the y-axis is split into two areas.

725 ence for 1000 Hz can neither be found in the HRTF
 726 differences nor in the HpTFs. The discussed devia-
 727 tions around 1600 Hz (see section 4.1) are above the
 728 band limits of the one-third octave band noise at 1000
 729 Hz. Reflections from legs or knees that might occur
 730 when seated are below these frequency limits. As the
 731 same hardware with synchronized settings were used
 732 at both sites, the digital headphone output levels mea-
 733 sured in Aachen and Oldenburg are comparable to a
 734 large extent and the deviation can already be found in
 735 this data, before applying any HpTF or HRTF data.
 736 Therefore, small differences between the rooms are ex-
 737 pected to cause the mismatch around 1 kHz (see [13]
 738 for a detailed discussion).

739 The effect of probe tube misplacements, as described
 740 in the sections above, on the listening test results is
 741 minimized as they cancel out in the divisions of HpTF
 742 by HRTF data as described in equation 1. This can
 743 also be seen in figure 6, at least for the HD650 and
 744 the DT770.

745 The high variability in the listening test results for
 746 the ER4 insert earphones can on the hand be found
 747 in the HpTFs (see section 3.2.2) showing a high vari-
 748 ability due to repositioning of the earphones, and on
 749 the other hand in any level plots of the listening test
 750 results (figures 5 and 6). The high number of reposi-
 751 tioning of the headphones during the listening test is
 752 assumed to increase the expected variability especially
 753 as no feedback regarding the seal of the earphones is
 754 given. The uen17 stimulus includes frequencies down
 755 to 20 Hz and is therefore most critical to low frequency

leakage which is stated as the cause for the differences between the headphones in both rooms.

Measuring the sound pressure levels with equipped probe tubes during the whole listening test would minimize the uncertainties regarding real sound pressure levels at the eardrum, but increases the effort (and testing time) drastically as a good fit of the microphones has to be verified before every stimulus presentation due to the risk of microphone repositioning with headphone handling. For further understanding of the insert earphone results, a more robust measurement estimation for the sound pressure level at the eardrum has to be used and repositioning of the earphones has to be done with more control over correct fitting and reproducibility. A test device including a microphone would be an option as in e.g. Hiipakka et al. [28].

A preceding pilot study by the authors [29], presenting a similar loudness balancing experiment, showed a significant difference around 250 Hz between the use of HD650 and DT770 when calculating the eardrum levels with KEMAR HpTFs and HRTFs. The same can be found in the results gathered in this study: When using the measured digital gains together with KEMAR HpTF and HRTF data, the difference occurs again. This indicates that individual eardrum level estimation affects the outcome of loudness balancing, especially for lower frequencies when fitting becomes more important.

5 Conclusion and outlook

The study presented confirms the comparability of findings between laboratories when measuring transfer functions and highlights crucial points in the procedures. Even though the approaches of measuring HRTF datasets were very different, the differences in the results are considerably small. Systematic, moderate deviations appear to be related to the posture of the subjects, which typically is influenced by the set-up and the desire to fix the subjects head to the reference point of the measurement.

For the measurement of HpTFs, both laboratory sites used the same approach and the same hardware. Consequently, the measured data is very alike in a frequency range up to approx. 7 kHz. Deviations at higher frequencies up to 10 dB probably stem from differences in the obtained microphone sensitivities that apparently do not correspond exactly to the difference between microphones and the equalization of the HpTFs with these sensitivities. As the sensitivities were measured only once but used on all measurements at one laboratory site, their influence is highly systematic. For the three different headphones under test, the open HD650 exhibited the flattest frequency response and smallest repositioning variations. The closed DT770 has a noticeable dip around 200 Hz and repositioning induced more variability towards lower

frequencies as the closed fit is more sensitive to fitting. The ER4 insert earphones highly depend on the fitting of the sealing of the ear canal using double-dome silicon plugs. This fitting was further influenced by the presence of the probe tubes and led to high variations between labs and between repositioning, the latter particularly towards lower frequencies. However, between the frequency range of about 900 to 3500 Hz the ER4 exhibited in reproducible HpTFs. Towards higher frequencies variability increases for all headphones due to shifted peaks and notches in the transfer functions.

Last, the influence of the probe tube position as one possible source of inaccuracy may lead to rather large deviations between measured transfer functions across sites. Yet, this effect cancels out in loudness balancing tests when HpTF and HRTF measurements are done with the same placing of the probe tubes, i.e. they stay fixed between both measurements.

On the one hand, the influence of the transfer functions on the loudness balancing results can be shown for deviations around 12 kHz, where differences in microphone sensitivities lead to high deviations in HpTF measurements between the laboratory sites and consequently in high deviations found for the loudness mismatch at this frequency. Also, the use of individual measurements clears the difference between the use of the HD650 and the DT770 at lower frequencies. On the other hand, deviations in transfer functions can not explain different cross-site differences of the loudness mismatch at 1000 Hz.

The gathered HRTF and HpTF data sets [30] can be used for a more thorough investigation of general (cross-site) measurement accuracy, while the present investigation was focussed mainly on explaining differences in loudness balancing. The data shown here solely focuses on the frontal direction and magnitude differences. Time and phase information, interaural cues as well as influences of incidence angles over the whole sphere can be taken into account. For each participant, blocked ear canal measurements were also taken (except for the insert earphones) and can be compared to the presented eardrum measurements.

Data Availability Statement

The measured head-related and headphone transfer functions [30] as well as the listening test results (levels of equal loudness) [31] are publicly available.

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868 References

- 869 [1] Jens Blauert, editor. *Communication Acoustics*.
870 Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg,
871 2005.
- 872 [2] Song Li and Jürgen Peissig. Measurement of
873 Head-Related Transfer Functions: A Review.
874 *Applied Sciences*, 10(14):5014, jul 2020.
- 875 [3] Abhijit Kulkarni and H. Steven Colburn. Vari-
876 ability in the characterization of the head-
877 phone transfer function. *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*,
878 107(2):1071–1074, 2000.
- 879 [4] Alexander Lindau and Fabian Brinkmann. Per-
880 ceptual evaluation of headphone compensation
881 in binaural synthesis based on non-individual
882 recordings. *J. Audio Eng. Soc.*, 60(1/2):137–142,
883 2012.
- 884 [5] Henrik Møller, Dorte Hammershøi, Clemen Boje
885 Jensen, and Michael Friis Sørensen. Transfer
886 characteristics of headphones measured on hu-
887 man ears. *J. Audio Eng. Soc.*, 43(4):203–217,
888 apr 1995.
- 889 [6] Florian Völk. Inter- and Intra-Individual Vari-
890 ability in the Blocked Auditory Canal Transfer
891 Functions of Three Circum-Aural Headphones.
892 In *Journal of the Audio Engineering Society*, vol-
893 ume 62, pages 315–323, New York, USA, jun
894 2014.
- 895 [7] Michael Vorländer. Acoustic load on the ear
896 caused by headphones. *The Journal of the Acous-
897 tical Society of America*, 107(4):2082–2088, 2000.
- 898 [8] Areti Andreopoulou, Durant R. Begault, and
899 Brian F. G. Katz. Inter-laboratory round robin
900 HRTF measurement comparison. *IEEE J. Sel.
901 Topics Signal Process.*, 9(5):895–906, 2015.
- 902 [9] Henrik Møller, Michael Friis Sørensen, Dorte
903 Hammershøi, and Clemens Boje Jensen. Head-
904 related transfer functions of human subjects. *J.
905 Audio Eng. Soc.*, 43(5):300–321, 1995.
- 906 [10] Klaus A. J. Riederer. Repeatability analysis of
907 head-related transfer function measurements. In
908 *105th AES Convention*, San Francisco, USA, sep
909 1998.
- 910 [11] Areti Andreopoulou, Agnieszka Roginska, and
911 Hariharan Mohanraj. Analysis of the Spectral
912 Variations in Repeated Head-Related Transfer
913 Function Measurements. *International Confer-
914 ence in Auditory Displays (ICAD)*, pages 213–
915 218, 2013.
- [12] Edgar A. G. Shaw. Earcanal Pressure Gener- 916
ated by Circumaural and Supraaural Earphones. 917
*The Journal of the Acoustical Society of Amer- 918
ica*, 39(3):471–479, mar 1966. 919
- [13] Florian Denk, Michael Kohnen, Josep Llorca- 920
Bofí, Michael Vorländer, and Birger Kollmeier. 921
The ‘missing 6 dB’ revisited: Influence of room 922
acoustics and binaural parameters on the loud- 923
ness mismatch between headphones and loud- 924
speakers. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 2021. 925
- [14] Leo L. Beranek. *Acoustic Measurements*. John 926
Wiley and Sons, Inc, New York, 1949. 927
- [15] Wilden A. Munson and Francis M. Wiener. In 928
Search of the Missing 6 dB. *Journal of the Acous- 929
tical Society of America*, 24(5):498–501, 1952. 930
- [16] Hugo Fastl, W. Schmid, Günther Theile, and 931
Eberhard Zwicker. Schallpegel im Gehörgang 932
für gleichlaute Schalle aus Kopfhörern oder Laut- 933
sprechern. In *Fortschritte der Akustik - DAGA 934
1995*, 1985. 935
- [17] Florian Völk and Hugo Fastl. Locating the miss- 936
ing 6 dB by loudness calibration of binaural syn- 937
thesis. *131st Audio Engineering Society Conven- 938
tion 2011*, 1:479–490, 2011. 939
- [18] Florian Denk, Stephan M. A. Ernst, Stephan D. 940
Ewert, and Birger Kollmeier. Adapting hearing 941
devices to the individual ear acoustics: Database 942
and target response correction functions for var- 943
ious device styles. *Trends in Hearing*, 22:1–19, 944
2018. 945
- [19] Florian Denk, Jan Heeren, Stephan D. Ew- 946
ert, Birger Kollmeier, and Stephan M A Ernst. 947
Controlling the Head Position during individual 948
HRTF Measurements and its Effect on Accuracy. 949
DAGA 2017 Kiel, pages 1085–1088, 2017. 950
- [20] Florian Denk, Birger Kollmeier, and Stephan D. 951
Ewert. Removing Reflections in Semianechoic 952
Impulse Responses by Frequency-Dependent 953
Truncation. *Journal of the Audio Engineering 954
Society*, 66(3):146–153, mar 2018. 955
- [21] Jan-Gerrit Richter. *Fast Measurement of Individ- 956
ual Head-Related Transfer Functions*. PhD the- 957
sis, RWTH Aachen University, Germany, 2019. 958
- [22] Bruno Masiero and Janina Fels. Perceptually ro- 959
bust headphone equalization for binaural repro- 960
duction. In *130th AES Convention, Convention 961
Paper 8388*, London, UK, 2011. 962
- [23] IEC International Electrotechnical Commission. 963
IEC 61094-8: Measurement microphones - Part 964
8: Methods for determining the free-field sensi- 965
tivity of working standard microphones by com- 966
parison, 2012. 967

- 968 [24] Eberhard Zwicker. Subdivision of the audible fre-
969 quency range into critical bands (Frequenzgrup-
970 pen). *J. Acoust. Soc. Am. (Letter to the Editor)*,
971 33(2):248, 1961.
- 972 [25] György Wersényi and András Illényi. Differences
973 in Dummy-head HRTFs caused by the Acoustical
974 Environment Near the Head. *Electronic Journal
975 of "Technical Acoustics" (EJTA)*, 1:1–15, 2005.
- 976 [26] Dorte Hammershøi and Henrik Møller. Sound
977 transmission to and within the human ear canal.
978 *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, 100(1):408–427, 1996.
- 979 [27] Sönke Mehrgardt and Volker Mellert. Transfor-
980 mation characteristics of the external human ear.
981 *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, 61(6):1567–1576, 1977.
- 982 [28] Marko Hiipakka, Miikka Tikander, and Matti
983 Karjalainen. Modeling of external ear acoustics
984 for insert headphone usage. *AES: Journal of the
985 Audio Engineering Society*, 58(4):269–281, 2010.
- 986 [29] Michael Kohnen, Florian Denk, Josep Llorca-
987 Bofí, Michael Vorländer, and Birger Kollmeier.
988 Loudness in different rooms versus headphone re-
989 production: Is there a mismatch even after care-
990 ful equalization? *Proceedings of the International
991 Congress on Acoustics*, 2019-Sept(1):7879–7886,
992 2019.
- 993 [30] Michael Kohnen, Florian Denk, Josep
994 Llorca-Bofí, Birger Kollmeier, and
995 Michael Vorländer. COAT - Cross-site
996 Oldenburg-Aachener transfer-functions.
997 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4556707>, 2020.
- 998 [31] Florian Denk, Michael Kohnen, Josep Llorca-
999 Bofí, Michael Vorländer, and Birger Kollmeier.
1000 Levels at eardrum and psychoacoustical
1001 data in loudness mismatch experiments.
1002 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4556669>, 2020.